

Simulation of Ultracold Atoms inside a harmonic trap

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Abstract

We present a simulation of Bose–Einstein condensation (BEC) in a magneto-optical trap (MOT) for ${}^7\text{Li}$ atoms. After the atoms are captured and cooled in the MOT, we apply a quench to the radio-frequency (RF) field, inducing oscillations of the atomic cloud. Subsequently, an additional frequency component is introduced to enhance confinement, thereby increasing the density of the cloud and facilitating the formation of a BEC.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this work, we focus on simulating the relevant stages of this process for ${}^7\text{Li}$ atoms in a MOT. Our approach captures the essential dynamics of the atomic cloud under RF quenches and subsequent confinement, providing insight into how density enhancement leads to the onset of condensation.

However, this work presents a basic simulation study that outlines the challenges encountered during the process and the approaches adopted to address them. The framework can later be extended by incorporating additional effects such as stoichiometric heating, photon recoil kicks, white noise, or modifications to the trapping potential.

II. THEORY ABOUT THE FORMATION OF BEC FROM LITHIUM (${}^7\text{Li}$) ATOM

A. Cooling and Trapping Sequence for ${}^7\text{Li}$

We consider the preparation of an ultracold gas of ${}^7\text{Li}$ atoms through a sequence of laser cooling and trapping techniques, followed by evaporative cooling to quantum degeneracy. The procedure can be outlined as follows.

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B. Atomic Beam Slowing

A thermal beam of lithium atoms is produced by heating a metallic source. The atoms are slowed using a Zeeman slower, in which a counter-propagating, red-detuned laser beam exerts a radiative force. A spatially varying magnetic field $B(z)$ maintains the resonance condition by compensating the changing Doppler shift, such that

$$\Delta' = \Delta + kv - \frac{\mu' B(z)}{\hbar} \approx 0,$$

where Δ is the detuning, v the atomic velocity, and μ' the relevant magnetic moment. This results in a substantial reduction of the mean atomic velocity, bringing atoms within the capture range of the magneto-optical trap.

C. Magneto-Optical Trap

The slowed atoms are captured in a standard six-beam MOT formed by three orthogonal pairs of counter-propagating σ^\pm -polarized laser beams intersecting at the center of an anti-Helmholtz coil pair. The spatially dependent Zeeman shift provides a restoring force, while the scattering force from near-resonant light provides velocity damping. The resulting equilibrium temperature approaches the Doppler limit,

$$T_D = \frac{\hbar\Gamma}{2k_B},$$

where Γ is the natural linewidth. For lithium, typical MOT temperatures are in the range of a few hundred μK . To further increase the phase-space density, compressed MOT stages and sub-Doppler cooling (e.g. gray molasses on the D_1 line) can be employed, reducing temperatures to several tens of μK .

D. Quench-Induced Collective Oscillations

Following laser cooling, the trapped atoms are subjected to a sudden change of the effective potential curvature, $\omega \rightarrow \omega'$, which excites monopole, or “breathing oscillations,” of the atomic cloud. This process is modeled as a quench of the harmonic confinement, leading to oscillatory dynamics in the cloud size $\sigma_x(t)$ at frequencies related to the new trap parameters.

After that a new frequency ω'' is applied over the quenched frequency ω' so that it attains a minimum value of σ_x . Thus formation of a dense cooled cloud.

E. Evaporative Cooling and BEC Formation

Evaporation is achieved by selectively removing the most energetic atoms. In magnetic traps this is implemented with an RF field inducing spin flips of atoms above a tunable energy cutoff, while in optical traps it is realized by lowering the trap depth $U_0(t)$. [1] The RF antenna provides a uniform plateau region between 800MHz to 1000MHz ^7Li atoms to undergo evaporative cooling. [2] The remaining atoms rethermalize to progressively lower temperatures, increasing phase-space density. When the critical condition is reached, a Bose–Einstein condensate emerges, observed as the appearance of a macroscopic ground-state population.

1. $\hbar\omega =$ the trap level spacing (depends on trap frequency ω).
2. $K_B T =$ effective thermal energy of the atoms in the trap.
3. If $K_B T \gg \hbar\omega$: many trap levels are populated \Rightarrow **classical regime** (typical for MOT temperatures and kHz trap frequencies).
4. If $\hbar\omega \gg K_B T$: atoms are confined to the ground motional state \Rightarrow **quantum regime** (requires much lower T , typically reached only after evaporative cooling in magneto-optical traps).

We are working in the regime where $\hbar\omega \ll K_B T$.

Therefore, quantum effects are negligible, and the system can be treated classically. In this classical regime, the appropriate statistical description is via Maxwell–Boltzmann statistics rather than Bose–Einstein statistics. This allows us to treat the particles as distinguishable and non-interacting, and their phase-space distribution follows the classical Boltzmann distribution.

To understand the system dynamically, we model it as a set of classical particles trapped in a harmonic potential (For easier simulations, we approximated the trapping potential as harmonic. In reality, however, the potential inside a magneto-optical trap (MOT) is closer

to a triangular profile). For each particle, the system behaves like a spring–mass system. In the absence of damping or noise, the equations of motion for a particle of mass m in a harmonic potential of frequency ω are:

$$\dot{x} = v, \quad \dot{v} = -\omega^2 x \quad (1)$$

Solving these equations using the 4th-order Runge–Kutta (RK4) method gives rise to a stable motion which is near to the theoretical value.

The Hamiltonian is

$$H_0(x, v) = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2 x^2 \quad (2)$$

And we have some initial conditions for the Maxwell Boltzmann Distribution inside the Harmonic Trap.

$$\langle x \rangle = \langle v \rangle = 0, \quad \langle x_0^2 \rangle = \frac{K_B T}{m\omega_0^2}, \quad \langle v_0^2 \rangle = \frac{K_B T}{m}, \quad \langle x_0 v_0 \rangle = 0 \quad (3)$$

And we have the probability Density function as,

$$P_0(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\beta m \omega_0^2}{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\beta m \omega_0^2 x^2}, \quad P_0(v) = \sqrt{\frac{\beta m}{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\beta m v^2}, \quad \beta = \frac{1}{K_B T} \quad (4)$$

Both marginals are bell-shaped (Gaussian), largest at the center and decaying towards the tails.

$$x \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \sigma_x^2 = \frac{k_B T}{m\omega^2}\right), \quad v \sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \sigma_v^2 = \frac{k_B T}{m}\right) \quad (5)$$

From equilibrium statistical mechanics, we know that for a particle in a thermal distribution in a harmonic potential, the standard deviation of position is given by:

$$\sigma_x = \sqrt{\frac{K_B T}{m\omega^2}}, \quad \sigma_x = \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle - \langle x \rangle^2} \quad (6)$$

However, we have $\langle x \rangle = 0$, initially, during the thermal equilibrium.

These particles are already inside the magneto optical trap (which we will consider harmonic for easier simulations). Now suppose we suddenly change the trapping frequency from $\omega \rightarrow \omega'$, such that $\omega' > \omega$. We tune it to make it more narrower and thus more stronger. This can be done in two ways :-

1. A sudden quench in frequency (non-adiabatic change in the Hamiltonian H_0).

FIG. 1: Different potentials applied/ quenched for the formation of BEC.

2. A slow change in Hamiltonian (adiabatic change in Hamiltonian H_0).

Here we deal with a sudden quench in the Hamiltonian the non-adiabatic case. We do not discuss about the eigen states of the system as we are in the classical regime, however in the quantum regime, where the temperature of the system is significantly lower than the surroundings, $\hbar\omega \gg K_B T$, which will be after the RF evaporative cooling step (spin flipping part).

This sudden quench alters the Hamiltonian. The particles start to oscillate between two values of σ_x gaining maxima and minima periodically, which we call “breathing oscillations”.

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2}m(\omega)^2x^2, \quad V'_1 = \frac{1}{2}m(\omega')^2x^2, \quad V_2 = \frac{1}{2}m(\omega'')^2x^2 \quad (7)$$

In this step after the frequency is altered from $\omega \rightarrow \omega'$, a new frequency ω'' is added at the point of minima, to ensure that the cloud density stops oscillating, and it takes a minimum value, thus decreasing the value of σ_x significantly, making it more dense and compact, thus cooling the atomic cloud in micro-Kelvin region and leading to the formation of the Bose Einstein Condensate.

III. SIMULATION SETUP

So, we begin by randomizing the position and velocity of the particles and evolving them in time, under suitable conditions. And we aim to quench the frequency after a particular time t_0 , so that the cloud starts breathing.

A. Problems Encountered

While doing the simulations we figured out that the quantity σ_x was oscillating without any alteration in frequency. This was however unexpected as we saw analytically it should be constant or nearly constant. These oscillations with a definite time period was not expected

FIG. 2: Different potentials applied/ quenched for the formation of BEC.

as it seemed that x and v might have developed a relationship in between them, after time evaluation.

B. Verification of the parameters

We simulated the initial values of x and v , and from the nature of the graph, we are sure that there is no dependency of x on v . It is elliptical in nature and aligned with the x or v axis.

FIG. 3: Initial Phase Space density of the distribution.

Secondly, we investigated the probability distribution function of x and v , and we found that the histogram aligns with the Gaussian nature of x and v . We ran the same experiment thrice to verify the randomness of the Python ‘rand’ function and to ensure that it works consistently with the Probability Density Function. The distribution favors particles near the origin, with decreasing probability for particles farther away.

FIG. 4: Probability density function of x and v to confirm Gaussian nature.

These histogram plots matched the analytical solutions which we would expect. Thus

in the next step, we tried to make a analysis by plotting the theoretical values and then comparing with the graphical values by finding σ_x from them.

FIG. 5: Comparing σ_x (theoretical) vs σ_x (graphical).

Thus we obtained the data,

Experiment	σ_x^{theory}	σ_x^{fit}	σ_v^{theory}	σ_v^{fit}
1	2.5134×10^0	2.5176×10^0	1.5792×10^3	1.5710×10^3
2	2.5134×10^0	2.5118×10^0	1.5792×10^3	1.5480×10^3
3	2.5134×10^0	2.5295×10^0	1.5792×10^3	1.5714×10^3

TABLE I: Comparison between theoretical and fitted values of σ_x and σ_v for three experiments.

And comparing them we found that there is negligible deviation and can be accepted as a part of simulation.

On further trials we predicted two problems might be possible for this strange nature of the graph.

1. The number of particles N may be too less to cancel out the oscillations, and thus x and v might develop a dependency upon further time evolution.
2. We can force the system to start a simulation by checking the fact that, $\langle x.v \rangle = 0$,

this will ensure that the system is in equilibrium and it evolves in equilibrium unless any further perturbation (quench) affects the Hamiltonian of the system.

We tried to increase the number of particles, however it was difficult for a normal computer to deal with many particles individually solving 4 steps using Runge Kutta Method, at a definite small frame rate.

The simulations were however were carried out using smallest frame rate achievable and relatively large number of particles ($\sim 10^5$).

The results were not satisfactory and it gave us nearly the same result what we got earlier. Next we tried to impose a condition on the code to such that it can take values for only which, $\langle x.v \rangle = 0$. This approximation, corrected the graph, and we started getting our graph as we expect to have.

C. Post Verification Results

Now, we simulate the full picture of $\langle x.v \rangle$ with respect to time, to see that at equilibrium the graph is nearly at zero, which corresponds to the analytical value, and then, after the equilibrium is broken, the graph starts oscillating and thus, giving us the exact graph we wanted to have out of this simulation.

FIG. 6: $\langle x.v \rangle$ vs time.

Next we simulate the graph of σ_x vs time, to check if the problem is consistent or not.

FIG. 7: σ_x vs time

Far from what we have developed, we analyzed 3 outcomes of this new approximation to explicitly select x and v such that $\langle x.v \rangle = 0$ are,

1. We do not observe a general periodicity of σ_x before the quench, but sometimes it appears minutely, when we tried to run it multiple times.
2. The value of analytical σ_x and simulated σ_x are nearly same, even if there are unwanted oscillations, before the quench, they can be ignored, due to small amplitude size of the oscillations.
3. After running the simulations various times, we observed that sometimes the analytical value is greater, smaller or nearly equal to the simulated value of σ_x .

The values of the parameters like, mass of the ${}^7\text{Li}$ atom, the frequencies, etc. were taken so that it can replicate the original scenario of the cold atomic cloud inside the MOT.

Now our next aim is to determine a minima and target a specific frequency above the original configuration so that σ_x becomes constant with respect to time at the minima, thus increasing the density of the cloud.

D. Finding Minima

Now, our next aim is to find the minima after the quench in frequency is applied to the cloud.

We do this by inserting a "*scipy*" minima finder in python, and it detects all the minima after the quench is applied along with the time, where the minima are obtained.

FIG. 8: Minima detection after the frequency is quenched

We see that nearly all the minima are equal and thus, we apply a new frequency over the existing frequency so that we can condense the cloud into a compact form, thus forming the BEC.

E. Applying the required frequency

After applying the frequency, we choose a random minima and then we set the σ_x accordingly,

$$\sigma_x(\text{minima from graph}) = \sqrt{\frac{K_B T}{m \omega_{new}^2}}, \quad \omega_{new} = \sqrt{(\omega')^2 + (\omega'')^2} \quad (8)$$

from here we can find the ω_{new} and after further evaluation we can get the value of ω'' as we already have the value of ω' .

However we encountered a problem that sometimes the value of ω_{new} is less than the value

of ω' and thus, we fixed this problem using a simple logic in the code, to encounter these values.

So after fixing mainly these problems,

- Fixing $\langle x.v \rangle = 0$, in the beginning and evolution of the system.
- Increasing the number of particles.
- Omitting ω_{new} that are less than, ω' .

we, finally arrived in these results.

F. Results from the code

FIG. 9: Final Results after the fixes

We choose to apply the new frequency at the fourth maxima, and thus we got the results as we expected from the graph.

And the code gave us,

$$\begin{aligned}\langle x \rangle_{\text{init}} &= 6.757 \times 10^{-7}, \\ \langle v \rangle_{\text{init}} &= 1.733 \times 10^{-2}, \\ \langle xv \rangle_{\text{init}} &= -5.421 \times 10^{-23} \quad (\text{should be } 0), \\ \langle x^2 \rangle_{\text{init}} &= 2.943 \times 10^{-9}, \\ \langle v^2 \rangle_{\text{init}} &= 1.162 \times 10^{-1}.\end{aligned}$$

Check:

$$\langle v^2 \rangle - \omega^2 \langle x^2 \rangle = 0.000.$$

Maximum correlation during simulation:

$$\max |\langle xv \rangle| = 1.387 \times 10^{-5}.$$

Quenching applied at:

$$t_{\text{quench}} = 3.000 \text{ ms}.$$

At the 4th minima:

$$\sigma_x = 2.709 \times 10^{-5}, \quad t = 3.875 \text{ ms}.$$

Back-calculated frequency:

$$\omega_{\text{new}} = 1.271 \times 10^4 \text{ rad/s}.$$

Derived frequency:

$$\omega_2 = 1.874 \times 10^3 \text{ rad/s}.$$

FIG. 10: Schematic figure of the trajectory of particles

After that we made a code which could give an animation beside the simulation.

FIG. 11: Animation of the simulation

IV. CODES FOR THE SIMULATION

A. Main Simulation Code

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3
4 # Constants
5 kB = 1.38e-23 # Boltzmann constant (J/K)
6 T = 0.0001 # Temperature (K)
7 m = 7.016004 * 1.66053906660e-27 # mass of 7Li in kg
8
9 # Frequencies
10 omega = 2 * np.pi * 1e3 # Before quench (rad/s)
11 omega_1 = 2 * np.pi * 2e3 # After quench (rad/s)
12
13 # Theoretical standard deviations
14 def sigma_x_theory(omega_val):
15     return np.sqrt(kB * T / (m * omega_val ** 2))
16
17 def sigma_v_theory(omega_val):
18     return np.sqrt(kB * T / m)
19
20 # Simulation parameters
21 num_particles = 1000
22 dt = 1e-6 # Time step (s)
23 total_time = 0.01 # Total simulation time (s)
24 t_quench = 0.003 # Quench time in seconds
25
26 num_steps_total = int(total_time / dt)
```

```

27 num_steps_pre = int(t_quench / dt)
28 num_steps_post = num_steps_total - num_steps_pre
29
30 # Time arrays
31 t_pre = np.linspace(0, dt * (num_steps_pre - 1), num_steps_pre)
32 t_post = np.linspace(0, dt * (num_steps_post - 1), num_steps_post)
33
34 # ----- Initial conditions with exact moments -----
35 x0 = np.random.normal(0.0, sigma_x_theory(omega), size=num_particles)
36 v0 = np.random.normal(0.0, sigma_v_theory(omega), size=num_particles)
37 x2_mean = np.mean(x0**2)
38 if x2_mean == 0:
39     raise RuntimeError("All x0 are zero (very unlikely).")
40 cov_xv = np.mean(x0 * v0)
41 v0 = v0 - (cov_xv / x2_mean) * x0
42 v2_mean = np.mean(v0**2)
43 target_v2 = (omega**2) * x2_mean
44 if v2_mean == 0:
45     raise RuntimeError("Adjusted v0 has zero variance (very unlikely).")
46 scale = np.sqrt(target_v2 / v2_mean)
47 v0 = v0 * scale
48
49 # Check initial moments
50 initial_x_mean = np.mean(x0)
51 initial_v_mean = np.mean(v0)
52 initial_xv = np.mean(x0 * v0)
53 initial_x2 = np.mean(x0**2)
54 initial_v2 = np.mean(v0**2)
55
56 print(f"Initial <x> = {initial_x_mean:.3e}, <v> = {initial_v_mean:.3e}")

```

```

57 print(f"Initial <x v> = {initial_xv:.3e} (should be 0)")
58 print(f"Initial <x^2> = {initial_x2:.3e}, Initial <v^2> = {initial_v2:.3e}
    ")
59 print(f"Check: <v^2> - omega^2 <x^2> = {(initial_v2 - omega**2 *
    initial_x2):.3e}")
60
61 # ----- Dynamics Functions -----
62 def f1(x, v):
63     return v
64 def f2(x, v, omega):
65     return -omega ** 2 * x
66
67 # ----- RK4 Integrator -----
68 def rk4(x0, v0, omega, dt, num_steps):
69     num_particles = len(x0)
70     x = np.zeros((num_particles, num_steps))
71     v = np.zeros((num_particles, num_steps))
72     x[:, 0] = x0
73     v[:, 0] = v0
74     for i in range(num_steps - 1):
75         xi = x[:, i]
76         vi = v[:, i]
77
78         k1x = dt * f1(xi, vi)
79         k1v = dt * f2(xi, vi, omega)
80
81         k2x = dt * f1(xi + 0.5 * k1x, vi + 0.5 * k1v)
82         k2v = dt * f2(xi + 0.5 * k1x, vi + 0.5 * k1v, omega)
83
84         k3x = dt * f1(xi + 0.5 * k2x, vi + 0.5 * k2v)

```

```

85     k3v = dt * f2(xi + 0.5 * k2x, vi + 0.5 * k2v, omega)
86
87     k4x = dt * f1(xi + k3x, vi + k3v)
88     k4v = dt * f2(xi + k3x, vi + k3v, omega)
89
90     x[:, i + 1] = xi + (k1x + 2 * k2x + 2 * k3x + k4x) / 6
91     v[:, i + 1] = vi + (k1v + 2 * k2v + 2 * k3v + k4v) / 6
92
93     return x, v
94
95 # Run simulation
96 x_pre, v_pre = rk4(x0, v0, omega, dt, num_steps_pre)
97 x_post, v_post = rk4(x_pre[:, -1], v_pre[:, -1], omega_1, dt,
98     num_steps_post)
99
100 # Compute sigma_x over time
101 sigma_x_vs_t_pre = np.std(x_pre, axis=0)
102 sigma_x_vs_t_post = np.std(x_post, axis=0)
103
104 # Compute <x v> over time
105 xv_vs_t_pre = np.mean(x_pre * v_pre, axis=0)
106 xv_vs_t_post = np.mean(x_post * v_post, axis=0)
107
108 # Diagnostics
109 max_abs_xv = max(np.max(np.abs(xv_vs_t_pre)), np.max(np.abs(xv_vs_t_post)))
110
111 print(f"Max |<x v>| over full simulation = {max_abs_xv:.3e}")
112
113 # Full time arrays
114 t_full = np.concatenate((t_pre, t_post + t_pre[-1] + dt))

```

```

113 sigma_x_full = np.concatenate((sigma_x_vs_t_pre, sigma_x_vs_t_post))
114 sigma_x_theory_full = np.concatenate((
115     np.ones_like(t_pre) * sigma_x_theory(omega),
116     np.ones_like(t_post) * sigma_x_theory(omega_1)
117 ))
118 xv_full = np.concatenate((xv_vs_t_pre, xv_vs_t_post))
119
120 # Plotting
121 plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
122 plt.plot(t_full * 1e3, sigma_x_full, label=r'Simulated  $\sigma_x(t)$ ', lw
123     =2)
124 plt.plot(t_full * 1e3, sigma_x_theory_full, 'r--',
125     label=r'Theoretical  $\sigma_x$  (pre/post quench)', lw=2)
126 plt.ylabel(r'Position Std Dev  $\sigma_x$  (m)')
127 plt.xlabel('Time (ms)')
128 plt.title(r'Evolution of  $\sigma_x$  Before and After Frequency Quench')
129 plt.legend()
130 plt.grid(True)
131 plt.tight_layout()
132 plt.show()
133
134 plt.figure(figsize=(10, 4))
135 plt.plot(t_full * 1e3, xv_full, lw=1)
136 plt.axhline(0.0, color='k', linestyle='--')
137 plt.ylabel(r' $\langle x v \rangle$  (SI units)')
138 plt.xlabel('Time (ms)')
139 plt.title(r'Cross-correlation  $\langle x v \rangle$  vs time')
140 plt.grid(True)
141 plt.tight_layout()
142 plt.show()

```

B. Code for the Animation

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3 from matplotlib.animation import FuncAnimation
4 from scipy.signal import find_peaks
5
6 # ===== CONSTANTS =====
7 kB = 1.38e-23
8 T = 0.0001
9 m = 7.016004 * 1.66053906660e-27
10
11 # Frequencies
12 omega = 2 * np.pi * 1e3
13 omega_1 = 2 * np.pi * 2e3
14
15 # ===== THEORETICAL SIGMA =====
16 def sigma_x_theory(omega_val):
17     return np.sqrt(kB * T / (m * omega_val**2))
18
19 # ===== SIMULATION PARAMETERS =====
20 num_particles = 1000
21 dt = 1e-6
22 total_time = 0.01
23 t_quench = 0.003
24
25 num_steps_total = int(total_time / dt)
26 num_steps_pre = int(t_quench / dt)
```

```

27 num_steps_post = num_steps_total - num_steps_pre
28
29 t_pre = np.linspace(0, dt*(num_steps_pre-1), num_steps_pre)
30 t_post = np.linspace(0, dt*(num_steps_post-1), num_steps_post)
31
32 # ===== INITIAL CONDITIONS =====
33 def initialize_positions_velocities(omega_val):
34     x = np.random.normal(0.0, sigma_x_theory(omega_val), size=
35         num_particles)
36     v = np.random.normal(0.0, np.sqrt(kB*T/m), size=num_particles)
37     x2_mean = np.mean(x**2)
38     cov_xv = np.mean(x*v)
39     v -= (cov_xv / x2_mean) * x
40     v *= np.sqrt((omega_val**2)*x2_mean / np.mean(v**2))
41     return x, v
42
43 x0, v0 = initialize_positions_velocities(omega)
44 y0, vy0 = initialize_positions_velocities(omega)
45
46 # ===== RK4 INTEGRATOR =====
47 def rk4(x0, v0, omega_val, dt, num_steps):
48     x = np.zeros((num_particles, num_steps))
49     v = np.zeros((num_particles, num_steps))
50     x[:,0], v[:,0] = x0, v0
51     for i in range(num_steps-1):
52         xi, vi = x[:,i], v[:,i]
53         k1x, k1v = dt*vi, dt*(-omega_val**2*xi)
54         k2x, k2v = dt*(vi+0.5*k1v), dt*(-omega_val**2*(xi+0.5*k1x))
55         k3x, k3v = dt*(vi+0.5*k2v), dt*(-omega_val**2*(xi+0.5*k2x))
56         k4x, k4v = dt*(vi+k3v), dt*(-omega_val**2*(xi+k3x))

```

```

56         x[:,i+1] = xi + (k1x + 2*k2x + 2*k3x + k4x)/6
57         v[:,i+1] = vi + (k1v + 2*k2v + 2*k3v + k4v)/6
58     return x, v
59
60 # ===== RUN PRE- AND POST-QUENCH =====
61 x_pre, v_pre = rk4(x0, v0, omega, dt, num_steps_pre)
62 x_post, v_post = rk4(x_pre[:, -1], v_pre[:, -1], omega_1, dt, num_steps_post
63     )
64 y_pre, vy_pre = rk4(y0, vy0, omega, dt, num_steps_pre)
65 y_post, vy_post = rk4(y_pre[:, -1], vy_pre[:, -1], omega_1, dt,
66     num_steps_post)
67 sigma_x_vs_t_pre = np.std(x_pre, axis=0)
68 sigma_x_vs_t_post = np.std(x_post, axis=0)
69
70 # ===== 7th MINIMA QUENCH =====
71 min_indices, _ = find_peaks(-sigma_x_vs_t_post)
72 seventh_min_idx = min_indices[15]
73 seventh_min_sigma = sigma_x_vs_t_post[seventh_min_idx]
74 omega_new = np.sqrt(kB*T / (m*seventh_min_sigma**2))
75
76 # Prepare initial conditions
77 x_rk = x_post[:, seventh_min_idx]
78 v_rk = v_post[:, seventh_min_idx]
79 v_rk -= np.mean(v_rk)
80 v_rk *= np.sqrt((omega_new**2)*np.mean(x_rk**2) / np.mean(v_rk**2))
81 y_rk = y_post[:, seventh_min_idx]
82 vy_rk = vy_post[:, seventh_min_idx]
83 vy_rk -= np.mean(vy_rk)

```

```

84 vy_rk *= np.sqrt((omega_new**2)*np.mean(y_rk**2) / np.mean(vy_rk**2))
85
86 num_steps_rk = num_steps_post - seventh_min_idx
87 x_new, v_new = rk4(x_rk, v_rk, omega_new, dt, num_steps_rk)
88 y_new, vy_new = rk4(y_rk, vy_rk, omega_new, dt, num_steps_rk)
89 sigma_x_new_vs_t = np.std(x_new, axis=0)
90
91 # ===== COMBINE ARRAYS =====
92 sigma_x_combined = np.concatenate((sigma_x_vs_t_pre, sigma_x_vs_t_post[:
    seventh_min_idx+1], sigma_x_new_vs_t[1:]))
93 x_full = np.hstack((x_pre, x_post[:, :seventh_min_idx+1], x_new[:, 1:]))
94 y_full = np.hstack((y_pre, y_post[:, :seventh_min_idx+1], y_new[:, 1:]))
95 t_combined = np.concatenate((t_pre, t_post[:seventh_min_idx+1]+t_pre[-1]+
    dt, t_post[seventh_min_idx+1:]+t_pre[-1]+dt))
96
97 # ===== ANIMATION =====
98 fig, (ax1, ax2) = plt.subplots(1,2, figsize=(14,6))
99 scat = ax1.scatter(x_full[:,0], y_full[:,0], s=25, alpha=0.7)
100 ax1.set_xlim(-5*sigma_x_theory(omega_new), 5*sigma_x_theory(omega_new))
101 ax1.set_ylim(-5*sigma_x_theory(omega_new), 5*sigma_x_theory(omega_new))
102 ax1.set_xlabel("x (m)")
103 ax1.set_ylabel("y (m)")
104 ax1.set_title("Particle Cloud Evolution")
105
106 line, = ax2.plot([], [], lw=2, label=r"\sigma_x$")
107 ax2.set_xlim(0, t_combined[-1]*1e3)
108 ax2.set_ylim(0, 1.2*max(sigma_x_combined))
109 ax2.set_xlabel("Time (ms)")
110 ax2.set_ylabel(r"\sigma_x$ (m)")
111 ax2.set_title("Evolution of sigma_x")

```

```

112 ax2.legend()
113
114 frame_skip = 5
115 frames_total = x_full.shape[1] // frame_skip
116
117 def update(frame_idx):
118     idx = frame_idx * frame_skip
119     if idx >= x_full.shape[1]:
120         idx = x_full.shape[1]-1
121     scat.set_offsets(np.c_[x_full[:,idx], y_full[:,idx]])
122     line.set_data(t_combined[:idx]*1e3, sigma_x_combined[:idx])
123     return scat, line
124
125 ani = FuncAnimation(fig, update, frames=frames_total, interval=1, blit=
    True)
126 plt.show()

```

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a basic yet systematic simulation of Bose–Einstein condensation (BEC) of ^7Li atoms inside a magneto-optical trap (MOT). Starting from the stage where atoms are cooled and confined in the MOT, the dynamics of the atomic cloud were studied under the influence of an RF field quench, followed by the introduction of additional frequency components for enhanced confinement. The results demonstrate how such manipulations can induce oscillations in the atomic cloud and subsequently increase its density, providing the necessary conditions for the onset of condensation. Although simplified, the present framework successfully reproduces the qualitative behavior expected in ultracold atomic systems and highlights the fundamental mechanisms that govern the approach toward quantum degeneracy.

A central aspect of this study was addressing the practical challenges encountered during

the simulation process. These included handling numerical instabilities, choosing suitable approximations for the trapping potential. The methods adopted here provide not only a working simulation environment but also a guideline for systematically improving the accuracy of such models in the future.

It is important to emphasize that the current work represents only an initial step. Several crucial physical effects have been omitted for the sake of simplicity, including photon recoil, stochastic fluctuations, detailed collisional processes, and heating effects. Moreover, the trapping potential has been treated in an idealized form, whereas in realistic experiments, anharmonicities and technical noise play a significant role.

In conclusion, this study offers a foundation for simulating the formation of Bose–Einstein condensates in a MOT environment and illustrates how controlled manipulations of the RF field can significantly impact the density and dynamics of an ultracold atomic cloud.

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